

CFD Analysis of lab-scale prototypes two-phase fluid flow twin-scroll compressor and expander

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Abstract

Computational Fluid Dynamics is a crucial tool for designing Positive Displacement machines. In this regard, we have developed a Computational Fluid Dynamics in-house solver to predict phase change phenomena inside the chambers of twin-scroll compressors and expanders handling two-phase fluid flow. The main numerical assessments of this work include velocity and pressure distribution, average inlet and outlet mass flow rates, vapor condensation and liquid evaporation phenomena, as well as isentropic, adiabatic, and volumetric efficiencies. These are essential for determining whether the machines experience excessive vibrations or work under overloaded conditions. The numerical results obtained with our solver align well with those obtained with a Deterministic Model found in existing literature. Additionally, the pressure and velocity distribution inside the scroll machines are similar to those reported in numerical studies of single-phase flow scroll compressors and expanders available in the literature.

Keywords: two-phase flow, twin-scroll machines, dynamic mesh solver, isentropic efficiency, adiabatic efficiency, volumetric efficiency

1. Introduction

The growing interest in renewable energy and sustainable technologies has motivated the development of systems that frequently operate with fluids in two-phase conditions. For instance, in geothermal power generation and organic Rankine cycle (ORC) systems, the working fluid often undergoes phase changes. Positive displacement (PD) machines are being increasingly adopted in these areas due to their ability to effectively maintain efficiency, robustness, and reliability, reduce size, enhance heat transfer, save energy, and efficiently manage phase transitions. Briola et al. [1] proposed a Combined Cooling, Heating, and Power (CCHP) cycle operating with two-phase devices for the compression and expansion processes of a single-component wet fluid. They also computed several performance indicators to evaluate the feasibility of serving tertiary and industrial end-users. In a subsequent contribution, Briola et al. [2] selected suitable working fluids for the CCHP cycle and proposed changes to the original cycle to improve and optimize it [3]. Such cycles are renowned for representing the most efficient engines in conjunction with two-phase expanders and compressors. Expanders, or turbines, convert the thermodynamic energy present in a fluid into mechanical power, which is then transmitted to generators to produce electricity. However, differently from traditional turbines and single-phase fluid expanders, two-phase fluid expanders can work in the wet vapor phase to produce higher mechanical and electrical power with the same mass flow rate, inlet and outlet pressure, and fluid quality at the

inlet. Besides, two-phase fluid expanders may in principle work without lubricating oil, since the liquid phase of the working fluid may act as a lubricant. Moreover, the liquid phase may operate as a sealant, increasing the volumetric efficiency and reducing the leakages. Compressors, on the other hand, utilize mechanical power from variable-speed motors to elevate the pressure of the working fluid, effectively concentrating its energy and facilitating its transportation throughout the system. Unlike single-phase fluid compressors, two-phase fluid compressors can work in the wet vapor phase to simultaneously increase the pressure of both phases. In addition, they have several advantages compared to single-phase fluid compressors. The required mechanical power is lower at the same mass flow rate, inlet vapor quality, and inlet and outlet pressures. Besides, a control system for the outlet pressure is not necessary and a liquid-vapor separator at the inlet and a mixer at the outlet are not required. To this end, significant efforts have been made to advance machines capable of effectively operating with two-phase fluids consisting of liquid and vapor phases. Therefore, an accurate design of these two-phase machines is a crucial aspect to optimize their performances and achieve cost-effectiveness. In principle, experiments can be conducted to measure the test parameters that are necessary to characterize the performance of compressors and expanders [4, 5, 6]. However, model tests may be costly and unable to replicate certain critical scenarios. Additionally, they struggle to accurately capture the temperature and pressure distributions within the working chambers. In this regard, mathematical models and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations have been widely employed to investigate the complex fluid flow phenomena that occur while compressors and expanders are in operation.

Simplified mathematical models that describe the physics of the process phenomena occurring in compressors and expanders are based on ordinary differential equations of conservation of mass and energy applied to one or more control volumes that encompass the whole geometry of those machines. Those equations are supplemented with algebraic equations that define several phenomena and consider fluid suction, compression, and discharge [7]. Early works on the development of mathematical models for studying fluid flow and heat transfer phenomena in a compressor date back to the contribution of Prakash and Singh [8], Fujiwara et al. [9], and Fujiwara et al. [10], among others. They were among the first who laid the foundation of simplified mathematical formulations for modeling thermodynamics, mass and heat transfer, and fluid flow processes in Positive Displacement (PD) machines. Fujiwara and Osada [11] exploited a previously developed mathematical formulation [9] to optimize the design of a rotor profile of an oil-injected screw compressor. Stošić et al. [12] also investigated the influence of oil injection in a screw compressor and validated their numerical results with experiments. Seshaiyah et al. [13] studied the influence of oil injection on the operating parameters and volumetric and adiabatic efficiencies of a twin-screw compressor. Bell et al. [14] scrutinized the physical effects occurring in scroll compressors and expanders with liquid flooding and compared their theoretical predictions with experimental results [15]. Chen et al. [16, 17] integrated a detailed model of a compression process into an overall model for a scroll compressor. They computed the temperature and pressure of the refrigerant in different compressor chambers, the temperature distribution in the scroll wraps, and other components of the compressor. Besides, they also calculated the mass flow rate, power input, and discharge temperature. On the one hand, the leakages and the heat transfer severely affect the volumetric efficiency and the compression work. On the other hand, the scroll size and geometry affect the whole performance of the compressor. Zhao et al. [18] investigated a water injection scroll compressor utilized in the automotive fuel cell system, considering also the leakage and the heat exchange between the air and the water. They found that the discharge losses and the volumetric efficiency increase as the compressor

rotational speed increases. Besides, an increment of the mass flow rate of water increases the isothermal efficiency and decreases the discharge temperature at a minimum cost of an additional power input. Dutta et al. [19] studied the influence of the injection of liquid refrigerant on the performance of a scroll compressor. Specifically, they examined the influence of the injection ratio on the compressor power, suction mass flow rate, and adiabatic efficiency. Taniguchi et al. [20] were among the first to apply an analytical procedure to study the intake, expansion, and exhaust phases of a two-phase flow screw-type expander and compute its performance. More recently, Leclercq and Lemort [21] investigated the performance of a two-phase scroll compressor with emphasis on the pressure and mass flow rate evolution with the orbiting angle, the influence of the rotational speed, the pressure ratio, and the leakages on the isentropic efficiency. However, although simplified mathematical models allow for quickly computing physical parameters that are necessary to characterize the machine performances, they are unable to completely describe the underlying physics of the problem. The complexity of the flow within PD machines poses challenges since multiple flow regimes can occur within a confined working domain. For instance, the presence of phase-changing flows within the working chambers leads to the development of a film on the rotor surfaces, which can potentially reduce the volume of the working chamber.

To address such complex phenomena, numerical methods furnish an alternative and valid approach. Basha et al. [22] compared the performances of a screw compressor obtained with Ansys Fluent[®] and Ansys CFX[®] in terms of pressure, volume flow rate, and power. Their numerical experiments indicate that Ansys Fluent[®] is not only approximately three times faster than Ansys CFX[®] but the numerical predictions also agree better with experimental results. Randi et al. [23] carried out three-dimensional simulations of an oil-injected single-screw expander. They tracked oil droplets to investigate their trajectories and the formation of oil film growth on the wall of the expander, showing that the smallest droplets have a higher probability of reaching the working chamber providing an efficient lubrication. Sun et al. [24] simulated the fluid flow of a single-phase roots blower and validated their results with Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) measurements. Liu et al. [25] and Liu and Lu [26] investigated numerically the presence of spiral inlets and outlets on the fluid flow in a three-lobe blower, showing that the adoption of those geometrical configurations suppresses the pulsation of pressure, velocity, and temperature. Sun et al. [27] studied the fluid flow in a Roots pump for two different sizes of the inlet and outlet pipes and inspected the onset of vortices at the inlet and outlet pockets. In a different contribution, Sun et al. [28] investigated a Roots blower with a backflow design. Their numerical results reveal that if the backflow passage is properly designed the pressure pulsations, the shaft power, and the mass flow rate decrease significantly. Cavazzini et al. [29] analyzed the inner fluid dynamics of a scroll compressor focusing on the unsteady phenomena that occur during the suction and discharge phases and on the effects of the axial clearance on the fluid flow and machine performance. Wei et al. [30] examined the pressure and velocity distribution in a scroll expander with constant thickness, investigating also the flow phenomena that induce the vortices originating in the suction and expansion chambers. Emhardt et al. [31] first investigated the velocity field, pressure, and temperature distributions in a scroll expander with variable thickness. In a subsequent and more exhaustive contribution, Emhardt et al. [32] focussed on how the size of the radial clearance affects the isentropic efficiency, specific power output, and exergy of a variable thickness scroll expander. Song et al. [33] numerically studied the three-dimensional flow in a scroll expander with emphasis on the radial leakage flow through the axial clearance between the scrolls. Gao et al. [34] numerically examined the influence of the tip seal volumes on the performance of a scroll compressor. More recently, Fadiga et al. [35] developed an open-source

tool to mesh the geometry of a scroll compressor and coupled it with the open-source software OpenFOAM[®]. In a subsequent contribution, Fadiga et al. [36] simulated the single-phase fluid flow in a commercial scroll compressor for three operating conditions considering the influence of the radial gap size in under and over compression.

In this work, we numerically simulate the two-phase fluid flow in a lab-scale prototype compressor and expander and identify crucial design aspects for efficient and safe operations using the open-source tool OpenFOAM[®]. Inspired by the works of Fadiga et al. [35, 36], we developed an in-house Cavitating Dynamic Mesh Solver (CDMS) which is a transient cavitation solver based on the Homogeneous Equilibrium Model (HEM) [37] with barotropic closure [38] from which the compressibility of the liquid/vapor mixture is obtained. The solver considers mesh motion and allows for mesh topology changes. The specific objectives of the CFD simulations include the assessment of the capability of the HEM to predict condensation and evaporation phenomena and compute the pressure and velocity distributions inside the two-phase PD machines. To check the validity of the outcomes obtained from the CDMS, we compare the CFD results with those obtained by solving numerically the governing equations of a Deterministic Model (DM) available in the literature. Overall, the CFD and the DM results match well both in the case of the compressor and in the case of the expander. The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe in detail the governing equations of the HEM and the barotropic closure. In Section 3, we provide the algebraic relations that define the inner and outer boundaries of the fixed and mobile scrolls, describe the meshing strategy of the whole computational domain, and give some explanation concerning the numerical solutions of the governing equations and the associated boundary conditions. Besides, we also briefly summarize the main ideas and governing equations of the DM developed by Leclercq and Lemort [21]. In Section 4, we examine the CFD results and compare them with those obtained with the DM. In Section 5, we discuss our results and provide suggestions concerning how to improve the present outcomes. Finally, in Section 6 we conclude our paper.

2. Governing Equations

We employ the HEM with a barotropic closure and a Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equation solver to simulate the cavitating flow phenomena that occur in the compressor and the expander while they are in operation. The HEM assumes local kinematic and thermodynamic equilibrium between phases and instantaneous vaporization and condensation processes. Besides, liquid and vapor are assumed to be perfectly mixed in each control volume of the mesh, and the two-phase mixture is considered compressible. The main governing equations are:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho_m dV + \int_S \rho_m (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S) \cdot \mathbf{n} dS = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho_m (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S) dV + \int_S [\rho_m (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S) (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S)] \cdot \mathbf{n} dS = \\ & - \int_V \nabla p dV + \int_S \{ \mu_{eff} [\nabla (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S) + (\nabla (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S))^T] \} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_V \rho_m dV = \Psi_m \frac{D}{Dt} \int_V p dV \quad (3)$$

Equation (1) is the mass conservation equation, Equation (2) represents the momentum equation, and Equation (3) is a barotropic closure equation of state relating pressure and density. Here, ρ_m denotes the bulk mixture density, \mathbf{u} is the mixture velocity vector, t is the time, p is the pressure, and $\mu_{eff} = \mu + \mu_t$ is the effective viscosity. Besides, V denotes a moving control volume, S is the surface that bounds V , \mathbf{n} represents the unit normal vector, and \mathbf{u}_S indicates the velocity of the surface boundary. Since the orbital movement of the mobile scroll modifies the computational domain, the grid nodes undergo a displacement originating the relative velocity $\mathbf{u}_R = \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S$. According to Demirdžić and Perić [39] the Space Conservation Law (SCL) must be satisfied so that the moving mesh respects continuity. The SCL asserts that the sum of the volume fluxes through cell faces must be equal to the volume rate of change

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V dV + \int_S \mathbf{u}_S \cdot \mathbf{n} dS = 0 \quad (4)$$

One of the methods that satisfies both the mass conservation and the SCL is based on computing the volumes swept by a cell face in a time step. These volumes are subsequently utilized to calculate the volume fluxes [40]. The mass fraction of vapor in the fluid mixture is denoted by γ , which is calculated using the following relation:

$$\gamma = \frac{\rho_m - \rho_{l,sat}}{\rho_{v,sat} - \rho_{l,sat}} \quad (5)$$

where $\rho_{l,sat}$ and $\rho_{v,sat}$ are the density of the liquid and vapor at saturation conditions [41], respectively. Equation (3) is supplied with additional liquid and vapor equations of state,

$$\rho_v = \Psi_v p \quad (6)$$

$$\rho_l = \rho_l^0 + \Psi_l p \quad (7)$$

to model the mixture's compressibility Ψ_m . In this work, we model Ψ_m utilizing the Wallis linear model [42], based on the vapor void fraction:

$$\Psi_m = \gamma \Psi_v + (1 - \gamma) \Psi_l \quad (8)$$

to ensure that the physical limits of pure liquid $\gamma = 0$ and pure vapor $\gamma = 1$ are realized. Besides, Equation (8) also considers intermediate states, where both phases are present in the mixture. The first term of Equation (7) contains the initial state of the liquid density ρ_l^0 , computed as $\rho_l^0 = \rho_{l,sat} - p_{sat} \Psi_l$. The subscript m indicates the mixture. The mixture molecular viscosity μ_m is computed as follows:

$$\mu_m = \gamma \mu_v + (1 - \gamma) \mu_l \quad (9)$$

The mixture density ρ_m is calculated by considering the ratio of the vapor in the fluid using an additional corrective term:

$$\rho_m = (1 - \gamma) \rho_l^0 + (\gamma \Psi_v + (1 - \gamma) \Psi_l) p_{sat} + \Psi_m (p - p_{sat}) \quad (10)$$

For additional details, see Salvador et al. [38]. Finally, the turbulent viscosity μ_t is computed using the Shear Stress Transport (SST) model formulated by Menter [43].

Figure 1: Three-dimensional models of the a) compressor and b) expander. c) Close-up of the surfaces between the two scroll noses

3. Computational Procedure

3.1. Geometry Specifications

Figure 1 displays the three-dimensional views of the Computer-Aided Design (CAD) models of the prototype compressor and expander with their respective Inlet and Outlet ports. The mobile scroll moves with orbiting angles $\Phi_c(t)$ varying from $\Phi_c(t) = 0^\circ$ up to $\Phi_c(t) = 360^\circ$. To uniquely specify the scroll profiles and determine their position along the orbit, we utilize algebraic relations. For the outer profile of the fixed scroll, one has

$$x_{of}(\Phi) = r_b (\cos(\Phi + \Phi_{o0}) + \Phi \times \sin(\Phi + \Phi_{o0})) \quad (11a)$$

$$y_{of}(\Phi) = r_b (\sin(\Phi + \Phi_{o0}) - \Phi \times \cos(\Phi + \Phi_{o0})) \quad (11b)$$

For the inner profile of the fixed scroll, the expressions read as follows

$$x_{if}(\Phi) = r_b (\cos(\Phi + \Phi_{i0}) + \Phi \times \sin(\Phi + \Phi_{i0})) \quad (12a)$$

$$y_{if}(\Phi) = r_b (\sin(\Phi + \Phi_{i0}) - \Phi \times \cos(\Phi + \Phi_{i0})) \quad (12b)$$

With regard to the outer profile of the mobile scroll, one has

$$x_{om}(\Phi, \Phi_c(t)) = r_b (\cos(\Phi + \Phi_{o0}) + \Phi \times \sin(\Phi + \Phi_{o0})) + \Pi \times \cos\left(\Phi_{oe} - \frac{\pi}{2} - \Phi_c(t)\right) \quad (13a)$$

$$y_{om}(\Phi, \Phi_c(t)) = r_b (\sin(\Phi + \Phi_{o0}) - \Phi \times \cos(\Phi + \Phi_{o0})) + \Pi \times \sin\left(\Phi_{oe} - \frac{\pi}{2} - \Phi_c(t)\right) \quad (13b)$$

For the inner profile of the mobile scroll, the expressions are

$$x_{im}(\Phi, \Phi_c(t)) = r_b (\cos(\Phi + \Phi_{i0}) + \Phi \times \sin(\Phi + \Phi_{i0})) + \Pi \times \cos\left(\Phi_{ie} - \frac{\pi}{2} - \Phi_c(t)\right) \quad (14a)$$

$$y_{im}(\Phi, \Phi_c(t)) = r_b (\sin(\Phi + \Phi_{i0}) - \Phi \times \cos(\Phi + \Phi_{i0})) + \Pi \times \sin\left(\Phi_{ie} - \frac{\pi}{2} - \Phi_c(t)\right) \quad (14b)$$

where $\Phi_c(t)$ is the Crank Angle (CA). Table 1 summarizes the parameters needed to model

Parameter	Equations	Value	Units
r_b	[-]	3.2	[mm]
Φ_{o0}	$(0 \times \pi) / 180$	0	[rad]
Φ_{i0}	$(81 \times \pi) / 180$	1.414	[rad]
Φ_{oe}	$(1583 \times \pi) / 180$	27.615	[rad]
Φ_{ie}	$(1583 \times \pi) / 180$	27.615	[rad]
Th	$r_b \times (\Phi_{i0} - \Phi_{o0})$	4.525	[mm]
Π	$r_b \times \pi - Th$	5.528	[mm]

Table 1: Geometrical parameters of the scroll profiles of the compressor and expander

the mobile and fixed scrolls. The compressor and the expander rotate over two distinct orbiting periods computed from the rotational speed of each machine. The orbiting period of the compressor is $T_{op} = 0.0194$ [s] while the one of the expander is $T_{op} = 0.0114$ [s]. In Figure 2 we present the evolution of these profiles for four CAs.

3.2. Computational Domains

The whole computational domain has been first separated into two domains: the first domain, Domain 1, comprises the moving and fixed scrolls while the second domain, Domain 2, only consists of a fixed part of the working chamber, as indicated in Figure 3. Subsequently, utilizing the *blockMesh* utility implemented in OpenFOAM[®], we first generated a mesh in a cylindrical domain and then we intersected it with a stereolithography (STL) file containing the shape of Domain 2 of the machine, as shown in Figure 4 a) and b). The cut between the mesh and the STL geometry is realized using the utility *snappyHexMesh* also implemented in OpenFOAM[®], see Figure 5 a) and b). Afterward, we covered the curved profile of the geometry between the two scrolls contained inside Domain 1 with a structured mesh consisting of multiple blocks with different mesh densities utilizing the *blockMesh* utility, see Figure 6. Then, we meshed the outer fixed part of Domain 1 and merged it with the inner part previously meshed utilizing the OpenFOAM[®] utility *mergeMeshes*, as shown in Figure 7 a). Finally, we merged Domain 1 and Domain 2 to obtain the final whole computational domain which is covered by 412793 control volumes, see Figure 7 b). To ensure the continuity of the computational domain, we left a small minimum gap of 0.225 [mm] between the mobile and the fixed scroll. Figure 7 c) and d) show some additional details of the computational domain. This meshing tool here denoted as CDMS, considers the rotation of the mobile scroll by generating a structured mesh for each rotation angle and stores these meshes as separate files. Each mesh file contains the control points, that is, the coordinates, through which the grids have to pass during the rotation of the twin scrolls. Using the grid files as a reference, the CDMS updated the mesh position at each time step. The position of a node at each time step is determined according to the following relation:

$$x_{i,final} = \delta x_{i,AG} + (1 - \delta) x_{i,NG} \quad (15)$$

where x_i is the position of a node of the corresponding grid file. The indices AG and NG refer to the actual and the next grid file, respectively. δ is a blending factor that depends on the rotational velocity and on the time steps of the interpolation [35].

3.3. Numerical Model

The CDMS considers mesh motion and changes in mesh topologies and integrates the generated set of meshes with the *cavitatingDyMFoam* solver implemented in the open-source software

Figure 2: Profiles of fixed and mobile scrolls for four CAs: a) $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, b) $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, c) $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, d) $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$. The black lines indicate the profiles of the fixed scrolls and the red lines indicate the profiles of the mobile scrolls

OpenFOAM-v2021[®] to solve the governing equations described in Section 2. First, Equation (1), the continuity equation, is solved for ρ_m and this value is utilized to compute preliminary values of \mathbf{u} , γ , and Ψ_m by solving Equations (2), (5), and (8), respectively. The iterative PIMPLE algorithm solves for the pressure p and corrects the velocity field \mathbf{u} until the mass conservation equation is satisfied. The PIMPLE algorithm combines the Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operator (PISO) and the Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations (SIMPLE) algorithms. To this end, Equation (1), the mass conservation equation is transformed into an equation for the pressure using Equation (10)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \Psi_m p dV + (\rho_l^0 + (\Psi_l - \Psi_v) p_{sat}) \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \Psi_m dV \\ - p_{sat} \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \Psi_m dV + \int_S \rho_m (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_S) \cdot \mathbf{n} dS = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Figure 3: Definition of two domains: Domain 1 incorporates the fixed and the mobile scrolls and Domain 2 only includes a fixed portion of the whole working chamber

Once the continuity equation is satisfied, the values of the remaining properties are updated utilizing Equations (5), (8), and (10). The new values of γ , ρ , and Ψ are utilized to solve Equation (2). We discretize the divergence terms of the governing equations using the first-order Gauss Upwind scheme, and we use the second-order Gauss Linear scheme to discretize the gradient terms [44]. The first-order implicit Euler scheme is deployed to integrate the governing equations in time. Although it is a first-order discretization scheme, it is very stable and suitable for multiphase flow problems with complex domains. The time step is automatically determined by the solver and is limited by a maximum value of the Courant and the acoustic Courant number. They are defined as

$$Co = \max \left(\frac{|\mathbf{u}|}{\Delta x} \right) \Delta t \quad (17)$$

and

$$Co_{acoustic} = \max \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\Psi_m} \Delta x} \right) \Delta t \quad (18)$$

The Courant number indicates how much the information travels across a computational grid cell in a unit of time. In Equation (17), Δx is a characteristic size of a grid cell, and $|\mathbf{u}|$ is the magnitude of the fluid flow velocity. In Equation (18), $|\mathbf{u}|$ is replaced with the speed of sound of the mixture [38]. The flow field is initialized using boundary, initial conditions, and fluid properties. Table 2 lists the values of some variables used as boundary conditions for the numerical simulations and Table 3 lists the properties of the liquid and vapor phases of the working fluid obtained with the software REFPROP[®] [45]. At the Inlet and at the Outlet of the two-phase machines the pressure assumes fixed values while the *zeroGradient* boundary condition has been set for all the solid surfaces. This means that the pressure gradient is equal to zero in the direction perpendicular to the walls of the machine. With regard to the boundary conditions for the velocity field, the *zeroGradient* boundary condition has been specified at the Inlet and at the Outlet of both compressor and expander and a *noSlip* boundary condition, i.e., a zero velocity, has been set at the walls. Concerning the mass fraction, the *calculated* boundary

Figure 4: a) Mesh of a cylindrical domain and b) intersection between this mesh and the STL file containing a portion of the shape of the machine

condition has been set at the solid walls and at the Outlet, meaning that the physical variable is computed by the numerical solver and not imposed by the user. With regard to the square root of the turbulent kinetic energy k , a *fixedValue* boundary condition has been set at the Inlet and a *InletOutlet* boundary condition has been specified at the Outlet. This type of boundary condition is equivalent to the *zeroGradient* one, but it switches to *fixedValue* in the case of backflow. Regarding ω , the *fixedValue* and the *zeroGradient* boundary conditions have been set at the Inlet and Outlet, respectively. Finally, the cyclic arbitrarily coupled mesh interface boundary condition, *cyclicACMI*, is utilized to connect the boundaries of moving domains with those of the fixed ones. This type of boundary condition imposes a cyclic condition between a pair of boundaries and the variables are interpolated between them. Besides, the default wall functions for k and ω have been specified at the solid surfaces. Due to the complexity of the model, we neglect the presence of oil in the numerical simulations.

Variable	Compressor	Expander	Units
Inlet Pressure	1.6	5.4	[bar]
Inlet Quality	0.39	0.713	[-]
Outlet Pressure	8.9	1.6	[bar]

Table 2: Boundary conditions

Parameter	Liquid Phase	Vapor Phase	Units
Kinematic Viscosity	$2.374e^{-7}$	$4.743e^{-7}$	[m ² /s]
Density	1144.96	8.78	[kg/m ³]
Specific Heat	1249.31	854.41	[J/(Kg K)]
Prandtl Number	3.744	0.839	[-]

Table 3: Properties of the working fluid R134a

Figure 5: a) Front and b) back side of the meshed Domain 2

3.4. Deterministic Model

In this section, we summarize the main ideas and governing equations of the DM developed by Leclercq and Lemort [21]. The first step of the DM is to define polygons that precisely fit the shape of the different chambers of the scroll machines for an angle step of 1° . The areas of such polygons may be calculated as follows

$$A = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} x_i y_{i+1} - x_{i+1} y_i \quad (19)$$

x_i and y_i are the coordinates of the n points that form a polygon. The volumes of the polygons are obtained by multiplying their areas by the height of the scroll. The second step consists of interpolating the values of the volumes utilizing a 5^{th} order polynomial function

$$V = c_5 \theta^5 + c_4 \theta^4 + c_3 \theta^3 + c_2 \theta^2 + c_1 \theta + c_0 \quad (20)$$

In Equation (20), θ is the orbiting angle. By doing so the relative error between the volume obtained by computing the areas of the polygons and the interpolated one is approximately 0.8%, the derivative of the volume with respect to the orbiting angle can be straightforwardly computed, and control volumes (CVs) for each chamber are also readily defined. This interpolation strategy allows for a considerable reduction of the calculation time compared to the numerical computation of the volume at each angle step [21]. The core of the DM lies in the following assumptions:

- The fluid flow is considered homogeneous. This means that the properties of the mixture are computed using a linear combination between the properties of the liquid and vapor phases. Besides, both phases have the same speed.
- The fluid flow is considered in thermal equilibrium and therefore the liquid and vapor phases have the same temperature.

Figure 6: Computational mesh of the domain between the twin-scrolls

- The presence of the Inlet and Outlet tubes has not been included in the model.
- The presence of oil has been neglected.
- The radial and flank leakages have been modelled to consider friction losses.

Based on the previous assumptions the mass and energy conservation equations of the DM may be written as

$$\frac{dm_{CV}}{d\theta} = \frac{1}{\omega} \sum_f \dot{m}_f \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{dT}{d\theta} = \frac{-T \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial T}\right)_v \left[\frac{dV_{CV}}{d\theta} - v \frac{dm_{CV}}{d\theta}\right] - \sum_f h_f \frac{dm_{CV}}{d\theta} + \frac{1}{\omega} \sum_f \dot{m}_f h_f}{m_{CV} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial T}\right)_v} \quad (22)$$

T , P , and u indicate the temperature, pressure, and internal energy of the fluid. m_{CV} and V_{CV} are the mass and the volume of the fluid present in a control volume. \dot{m}_f and h_f represent the mass flow rate and specific enthalpy of the fluid calculated on a surface of the control volume [21]. Besides, we utilize the Clapeyron equation to compute

$$\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial T}\right)_v = \frac{h_g - h_l}{T(v_g - v_l)} \quad (23)$$

where h_g and h_l are the specific enthalpy of the gas and the liquid phases, respectively. Besides, v_g and v_l are the specific volume of the gas and the liquid phases. The fluid flow that crosses the control volumes is considered to be similar to the fluid flow in a convergent nozzle and is considered adiabatic, reversible, and compressible. To compute the mass flow rate of a two-phase adiabatic compressible flow inside a nozzle, Leclercq and Lemort [21] utilize the expression proposed by Chisolm [46].

Figure 7: a) Slice of the computational mesh obtained merging the grid generated between the twin scrolls and the grid of the outer part of Domain 1 on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis, b) Mesh of the entire computational domain, c) Close-up of the end tip of the scroll, and d) Close-up between the fixed and mobile scrolls

$$\dot{m} = \xi X_d C_d A_{th} \sqrt{\frac{2 \int_{P_{down}}^{P_{up}} v_e dP}{v_{e,down}^2 - \sigma v_{e,up}^2}} \quad (24)$$

where ξ and X_d represent the friction flow and the area correction factors, C_d denotes the discharge coefficient, and A_{th} is the throat area of the nozzle. The friction flow correction factor ξ incorporates the effects of the leakages. In addition, σ denotes the ratio of the downstream over the upstream areas. The effective volume v_e may be written as

$$v_e = [Q v_g + K_e (1 - Q) v_l] \left[Q + \frac{1 - Q}{K_e} \right] \quad (25)$$

where Q and K_e are the vapor quality and the effective slip ratio. The latter is defined as

$$K_e = \left[\Omega + \frac{(1 - \Omega^2)}{K - \Omega} \right] \quad (26)$$

In Equation (26) Ω denotes the mass fraction of the liquid that travels in the gas phase at the gas velocity, and the entrainment slip ratio may be written as

$$K = \Omega + (1 - \Omega) \sqrt{\frac{1 + \Omega(1 - Q) [v_l / (Qv_g)]}{1 + \Omega [(1 - Q)/Q]}} \sqrt{\frac{v_g}{v_l}} \quad (27)$$

for more details see [21]. The model is first initialized by obtaining the polynomial coefficients of the volume interpolation function so that the CVs can also be specified. Subsequently, Equations (21) and (22) are integrated using a forward Euler method, and the volumes of the CVs are also updated. The integration is iteratively carried out over one complete revolution of the machines until the difference of the values of the temperature and density in each CV between two subsequent iterations falls below a specific tolerance value [21].

4. Results

4.1. Compressor

Figure 8 shows the pressure distribution on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the whole computational domain for four representative CAs, $\Phi_C = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_C = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_C = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_C = 360^\circ$ over one typical revolution. The pressure reaches its peak close to the scroll noses and decreases toward the scroll tips in the vicinity of the boundaries. When the two scroll noses approach each other at approximately $\Phi_C = 90^\circ$, the compression process begins since a certain amount of fluid has entered the machine due to the suction process. The working fluid is compressed as the mobile scroll rotates and the pressure of a large region of fluid increases over the entire orbiting cycle. The pressure of the fluid results higher closer to the Outlet and gradually decreases toward the peripheral areas of the machine where the Inlet ports are located. Once the fluid has reached the designed value of the pressure and the mobile scroll has returned to its original position, the Outlet opens, the discharge phase begins, and the fluid pressure decreases. In Figure 9 we compare the average pressure distribution during one revolution of the mobile scroll in the discharge chamber obtained with the CFD simulations and by solving the DM. The value of the pressure remains almost constant during the whole revolution of the mobile scroll except for showing some random fluctuations due to unsteady flow phenomena. Brusque and small fluctuations are captured by the CFD simulations while the DM is only able to reproduce the significant change of the average pressure values occurring at approximately $\theta = 230^\circ$. Nevertheless, the trend of the average pressure over one orbiting period agrees well between the two models. On the one hand, the average value of the average pressure distribution during one revolution of the mobile scroll obtained with the CFD model assumes values approximately equal to 10 [bar]. On the other hand, the average value of the average pressure distribution during one revolution of the mobile scroll obtained by solving the DM is approximately equal to 8 [bar]. This indicates that the agreement between the CFD model and the DM is very good.

Figure 10 shows the variations of the vapor void fraction over one revolution of the orbiting angle on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the entire computational domain for four representative CAs, $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$. During the compression process, the presence of both liquid and vapor phases can be observed between the fixed and

mobile scrolls. The working fluid begins to condense and the vapor void fraction decreases in several areas of the working chamber. Specifically, a high concentration of the liquid phase is observed in areas where the pressure of the working fluid is high, for instance, close to the scroll noses, indicating that the fluid undergoes condensation phenomena. On the other hand, toward the tips of the compressor in the vicinity of the Inlet areas, the pressure decreases and the vapor void fraction increases, revealing that the working fluid evaporates. This is in accordance with the phase-change pressure-temperature diagram reported by Papon et al. [47], which shows that a large percentage of the mixture is in the liquid phase at high pressures. Figure 11 plots the volume average vapor void fraction inside the computational domain for eleven revolutions of the orbiting angle. The initial void fraction gradually declines from approximately 0.98 to approximately 0.68 after three revolutions, indicating that the fluid dynamics of the machine reaches a steady-state condition with the fluid repeatedly condensing and evaporating inside the compressor. Figure 12 presents comparative plots, albeit over only one revolution of the orbiting angle, of the vapor mass fraction γ at the Outlet obtained with the CFD computations and with the DM. The CFD results compare favorably to the results of the DM computations, showing that the vapor mass fraction assumes almost a constant value at the Outlet for the entire orbiting period. Specifically, the CFD simulations yield an average $\gamma_{av} = 0.04803$ and the DM computations deliver an average $\gamma_{av} = 0.04851$ with a discrepancy of only approximately 1%.

Figure 13 a) displays the mass flow rate and the averaged value of the mass flow rate over one orbiting period at the Inlet of the two-phase fluid flow compressor for one revolution of the orbiting angle. Besides, it also shows the pressure difference between the Inlet and the suction chamber. The mass flow rate at the Inlet pulsates and rapidly oscillates with the orbiting angle, reaching a peak at approximately $\theta = 180^\circ$. The maximum value of the mass flow rate computed with the CFD model is approximately equal to $1.20 [kg/s]$ while the one obtained with the DM is approximately equal to $0.5 [kg/s]$. Despite the significant deviation between the maximum value of the mass flow rate obtained with the two models, the CFD simulations produce an average Inlet mass flow rate approximately equal to $0.22 [kg/s]$ and the DM delivers an average Inlet mass flow rate approximately equal to $0.23 [kg/s]$. The discrepancy is approximately equal to only 4% confirming a very good agreement between the two models. The pressure difference between the Inlet and the suction chamber follows the same trend of the mass flow rate, oscillating and pulsating for one orbiting period. This pressure difference also reaches a peak at approximately the same revolution angle where the mass flow rate achieves its maximum, indicating that both phenomena are closely related to each other. Figure 13 b) exhibits the mass flow rate and the average value of the mass flow rate over one orbiting period at the Outlet of the compressor for one revolution of the orbiting angle. Moreover, it also shows the pressure difference between the Outlet and the discharge chamber. On the one hand, the mass flow rate computed with the CFD model presents a single and well-defined peak at approximately $\theta = 140^\circ$. On the other hand, the mass flow rate computed using the DM suddenly increases at approximately $\theta = 80^\circ$ reaching a peak of about $0.8 [kg/s]$. This peak persists until approximately $\theta = 200^\circ$ where the value of the mass flow rate declines. Also in this circumstance, the mass flow rate calculated by utilizing the DM severely underestimates the one obtained by employing the CFD model. However, the average value of the Outlet mass flow rate obtained with the CFD simulation is approximately equal to $0.23 [kg/s]$ and agrees favorably with the one delivered by the DM, being approximately equal to $0.24 [kg/s]$. The difference between the two models is only approximately equal to 4% and the very close values between the average mass flow rate at the Inlet and the Outlet indicate that the steady-state condition has been reached by the machine. The trend of the pressure

difference between the Outlet and the discharge chamber is also similar to the trend of the mass flow rate at the Outlet port over the entire orbiting period, exhibiting a peak at approximately the same orbiting angle and suggesting a close link between the pulsating pressure and the mass flow rate. This pulsating behavior is closely related to the perturbation of the pressure at the Inlet and the Outlet ports. These perturbations are provoked by inertial phenomena that originate during the discharging phase and cause the pressure drop to propagate back to the Inlet. The peaks of the mass flow rates at the Inlet and the Outlet ports originated due to a superposition of jets of mass travelling inside the working chamber [29], and by periodic hindrance effects of the mobile scroll on the Inlet and the Outlet of the machines [30].

Figure 14 displays the velocity distribution on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the computational domain for four representative CAs, $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$ for one revolution of the mobile scroll. The velocity of the fluid flow varies from very small values up to more than 100 [m/s] in the chambers of the scroll machine and the peaks of the velocity not only occur in the narrow gaps between the fixed and mobile scrolls but also in parts of the computational domain located close to the Inlet where the fluid is mostly in the vapor phase and it has sufficient space to develop. The visible large recirculation areas are induced by the interactions between the fluid that enters the compressor at the Inlet and the walls of the fixed and the mobile scroll. These strong interactions cause the flow to briskly change direction, originating vortices that gradually extend along the radial direction. In the vicinity of the Outlet, a high percentage of the fluid is in the liquid phase and the narrow spaces between the fixed and the mobile scroll do not permit the fluid to develop. Therefore, the velocity assumes low values except for the very small gaps between the fixed and the mobile scroll where the velocity of the fluid flow abruptly increases to satisfy the mass conservation equation.

Finally, in Table 4 we compare the average mass flow rates at the Inlet and the Outlet of the compressor over one orbiting cycle, the isentropic and volumetric efficiencies obtained with the CFD simulations, and the DM. Table 4 also lists the relative error between the results of the CFD simulations and the DM. The average Inlet and Outlet mass flow rates obtained with the CFD simulations are slightly lower than the ones obtained with the DM. Nevertheless, the values agree very well between both models. The isentropic efficiency measures the extent to which the refrigerant is compressed and stands for the ratio of the actual work done over the ideal work done in an isentropic process. The CFD simulations determine an isentropic efficiency equal to 71.25% and the DM computations produce an isentropic efficiency equal to 71.56%, indicating that the compressor can compress the refrigerant without significant losses. The volumetric efficiency measures how well the compressor delivers a desired volume of fluid at a given pressure and temperature. The volumetric efficiency obtained from the CFD simulations is equal to 100.3% and the one obtained from the DM is equal to 96.6%, revealing that the compressor can deliver the required volume of refrigerant with hardly any losses.

	CFD	DM	Units	Error [%]
Average Inlet mass flow rate	0.218	0.232	[kg/s]	6
Average Outlet mass flow rate	0.231	0.238	[kg/s]	2.74
Isentropic efficiency	71.25	71.56	[-]	0.43
Volumetric efficiency	100.3	96.6	[-]	3.78

Table 4: Average values of the Inlet and Outlet mass flow rates over one orbiting cycle. Isentropic and volumetric efficiencies of the compressor obtained from the CFD simulations and the DM

4.2. Expander

Figure 15 illustrates the pressure distribution on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the whole computational domain of the expander for four representative CAs, $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$. Similar to the case of the scroll compressor discussed previously, the pressure reaches a peak close to the scroll noses and then decreases toward the scroll tips in the vicinity of the Outlet ports. When the two scroll noses are apart at approximately $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, the expansion process begins. The working fluid expands as the mobile scroll moves and the pressure of a considerable portion of fluid decreases during the entire orbiting cycle, principally in the vicinity of the discharge chambers close to the Outlet ports. Once the mobile scroll returns to its original position, the suction phase begins again and a fluid at high pressure enters the machine. Figure 16 exhibits a comparison of the average fluid pressure in the discharge chamber obtained using the DM and the CFD model for one revolution of the orbiting angle. On the one hand, the results obtained with the DM model show a slight variation of the pressure in the discharge chamber during one revolution of the mobile scroll. On the other hand, the CFD results indicate that random and abrupt pressure fluctuations occur in the discharge chamber when the mobile scroll rotates. The CFD results show a minimum of the pressure at approximately $\theta = 120^\circ$ and a maximum at approximately $\theta = 240^\circ$. The pressure variations determined by the CFD computations range approximately between $p = 1.3 [bar]$ and $p = 2.3 [bar]$. Nevertheless, the trend of the pressure obtained utilizing the DM and the CFD model agrees qualitatively well.

Figure 17 presents the variations of the vapor void fraction on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the whole computational domain for four representative CAs, $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$. During the expansion process, both the liquid and vapor phases are present in the two-phase scroll machine. The mobile scroll rotates and expands the working fluid which begins to evaporate. Therefore, the concentration of the vapor void fraction increases in several areas of the working chamber. Specifically, the amount of the liquid phase remains high in the vicinity of the Inlet port but the vapor void fraction increases in a large portion of the expander. The concentration of the vapor void fraction results maximized toward the peripheral areas of the expander close to the Outlet ports. As we have already examined, in the proximity of the scroll noses the pressure of the working fluid is high since the fluid has just entered the scroll machine. However, it decreases toward the vicinity of the Outlet ports, as a result of the expansion process. Also in the case of the expander, high-pressure values lead the vapor phase to condensation, and low-pressure values induce the liquid phase to evaporate, as indicated by the phase change pressure-temperature diagram of Papon et al. [47]. Figure 18 plots the volume average vapor mass fraction γ_{av} inside the computational domain for seven revolutions of the orbiting angle. The vapor mass fraction gradually increases from $\gamma_{av} = 0.024$ to approximately $\gamma_{av} = 0.60$ at $\Phi_c = 220^\circ$, and then it decreased to about $\gamma_{av} = 0.58$ after the first revolution. The average vapor mass fraction inside the expander assumes an average value of approximately $\gamma_{av} = 0.59$ already after the first revolution. This indicates that the expander reaches a steady-state condition and vapor condensation and evaporation phenomena periodically occur within the working chambers. Figure 19 displays the average vapor mass fraction at the Outlet surface for one revolution of the orbiting angle obtained with the CFD simulations and using the DM. The CFD results compared favorably to DM computations since the CFD computations yield an average $\gamma_{O,av} = 0.8044$ over the orbiting period and the DM simulations produce an average $\gamma_{O,av} = 0.8179$ for one orbiting period. The difference is only approximately equal to 1.65 %.

Figure 20 a) plots the Inlet mass flow rate of the expander, the average value of the Inlet mass flow rate over one orbiting period, and the pressure difference between the Inlet and the suction

chamber for one revolution of the orbiting angle. The Inlet mass flow rate obtained with the CFD simulations sharply pulsates as the orbiting angle increases from $\Phi_c = 0^\circ$ to $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$, reaching a maximum value of approximately 0.46 [kg/s] . The Inlet mass flow rate obtained with the DM also varies with the orbiting angle but only at approximately $\Phi_c = 95^\circ$ strong oscillations occur. Moreover, an isolate minimum arises at approximately $\Phi_c = 250^\circ$. Nevertheless, the average value of the Inlet mass flow rate over one revolution obtained with the CFD simulations $m_{I,av} = 0.359 \text{ [kg/s]}$ agrees well with the one computed with the DM $m_{I,av} = 0.356 \text{ [kg/s]}$. The discrepancy between the two values is less than 1%. The pressure difference between the Inlet and the suction chamber also undergoes random fluctuations for the whole orbiting period reflecting the same trend of the Inlet mass flow rate. Figure 20 b) plots the Outlet mass flow rate, the average value of the Outlet mass flow rate over one orbiting period, and the pressure difference between the Outlet and the discharge chamber of the expander for one revolution of the orbiting angle. The Outlet mass flow rate computed with the CFD model reaches the highest values at approximately $\Phi_c = 230^\circ$ and displays small and continuous fluctuations over the entire orbiting period. On the other hand, the Outlet mass flow rate calculated with the DM shows almost no fluctuations during the revolution of the mobile scroll, with a minimum at approximately $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$ and a peak at about $\Phi_c = 250^\circ$. The average value of the Outlet mass flow rate obtained with the CFD simulation $m_{O,av} = 0.3632 \text{ [kg/s]}$ matches well with the average value delivered by the DM computations, $m_{O,av} = 0.3477 \text{ [kg/s]}$. The deviation is only approximately 4.27%, indicating again a good agreement between the CFD model and the DM. The trend of the difference between the pressure at the Outlet and the discharge chamber also mirrors the trend of the pulsating mass flow rate at the Outlet for the entire orbiting period, hinting at a close relationship between both phenomena.

Figure 21 illustrates the velocity distribution on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the whole computational domain for four representative CAs, $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$. Analogously to the case of the scroll compressor, the velocity of the fluid flow in the expander varies in a wide range from values very close to 0 [m/s] up to values higher than 150 [m/s] . The velocity peaks are higher in the expander than in the compressor due to the higher angular velocity. Moreover, the velocity reaches the peaks also in the gaps between the fixed and mobile scrolls where the concentration of the vapor phase is high. Besides, the velocity assumes high values close to the Outlet where the vapor void fraction is high and the fluid has sufficient space to develop. Wide recirculation areas are induced by the interactions between the fluid that leaves the expander at the Outlet and the surfaces of the scrolls, causing the flow to abruptly deviate from its original direction. Vortices arise and gradually extend in the radial and azimuthal directions. Close to the Inlet, the fluid mostly is in the liquid phase and the tiny spaces between the scrolls do not allow the fluid to develop. Thereby, the velocity assumes much lower values compared to other locations within the expander.

Table 5 lists the average Inlet and Outlet mass flow rates over one orbiting period, and the adiabatic and volumetric efficiencies obtained from the CFD simulations and the DM. Besides, Table 5 also lists the error between the CFD and DM results. The average Inlet and Outlet mass flow rates obtained from the CFD simulations are slightly higher than the ones obtained from the DM. Nevertheless, the values agree well and the error is less than 5%. The adiabatic efficiency measures how efficiently the expander converts the energy of the working fluid into useful work. The adiabatic efficiency is calculated as the actual work done by the expander over the theoretical maximum work done in adiabatic conditions. The CFD simulations yield an adiabatic efficiency equal to 70.52% and agree well with the value of the DM, 64.68%. The volumetric efficiency

obtained from the CFD simulations is 152.12% and the one obtained from the DM is 148.26%, revealing that the expander is subjected to leakage losses that are typical for scroll machines. The values of the adiabatic and volumetric efficiencies suggest that the prototype of the expander is well-designed, it can efficiently expand the working fluid, and deliver the desired amount of refrigerant at the required pressure and temperature.

	CFD	DM	Units	Error [%]
Average Inlet mass flow rate	0.359	0.356	[kg/s]	0.84
Average Outlet mass flow rate	0.363	0.348	[kg/s]	4.46
Adiabatic efficiency	70.56	64.68	[-]	9.03
Volumetric efficiency	152.12	148.26	[-]	2.60

Table 5: Average values of the mass flow rates at the Inlet and Outlet over one orbiting cycle. Isentropic and volumetric efficiencies of the expander obtained from the CFD simulations and the DM

5. Discussion

In this work, we numerically investigated the multiphase flow phenomena occurring in lab-scale twin-scroll compressors and expanders during their operations. To this end, we developed the CDMS, a transient cavitating solver suitable for simulating the fluid flow within scroll machines. The CDMS has been realized within the OpenFOAM[®] environment by combining a set of grids generated using the OpenFOAM[®] utilities *blockMesh* and *snappyHexMesh* with the *cavitatingDyMFoam* solver already implemented in OpenFOAM[®]. The final meshes have values of skewness, orthogonality, aspect-ratio, and many other parameters that satisfy the OpenFOAM[®] standards. Besides, the values of skewness, orthogonality, and aspect ratio of our grids listed in Table 6 are similar to those reported by Fadiga et al. [35] listed in Table 7.

During the compression and expansion processes, the presence of the vapor and liquid phases is noticeable between the fixed and the mobile scrolls, indicating that condensation and evaporation phenomena occur within the machines. Specifically, a low vapor volume fraction is present in the chambers of the machines close to the scroll noses, while a high vapor volume fraction is observable in the vicinity of their peripheral areas. This is associated with the pressure distribution within the compressor and the expander as shown by Papon et al. [47]. On the one hand, in regions where the pressure of the working fluid is high, the volume fraction of the liquid phase is high. On the other hand, in regions where the pressure of the fluid is low, the vapor volume fraction assumes high values. Cavazzini et al. [29] and Gao et al. [34] carried out transient three-dimensional CFD simulations of a scroll compressor with two commercial solvers, that is, Ansys CFX[®] and PumpLinx[®], and found an analogous pressure distribution within the working chambers. Wei et al. [30], Emhardt et al. [32], Emhardt et al. [31], Song et al. [33], Singh et al. [48] carried out transient three-dimensional CFD simulations of a scroll expander and found comparable pressure distributions. Their numerical results also yield maximum values of the pressure in the vicinity of the scroll noses and progressively decaying values toward the peripheral areas of the scroll machine. Our numerical results reveal that the pressure range of the compressor varies approximately between a minimum of 0.4 [bar] up to a maximum of 11 [bar] and the pressure of the expander ranges approximately between 3.5 [bar] up to a maximum of 6 [bar], confirming that the machines are not overloaded under the current working conditions and they can be safely operated. Our numerical simulations display a pulsating profile of the difference between the average pressure at the Inlet and in the suction chamber over one orbiting

period of the scroll machines. Besides, we also obtained a pulsating profile by computing the difference between the average pressure at the Outlet and in the discharge chamber for one revolution of the mobile scroll of the two-phase machines. The numerical study of Cavazzini et al. [29] also confirms a rapidly oscillating profile of the average pressure at the Inlet and at the Outlet ports of a scroll compressor. Besides, Wei et al. [30] also reports a pulsating pressure profile in the vicinity of the Inlet and of the Outlet of a scroll expander while it is in operation. Moreover, they also monitored and tracked the pressure profile with time at different locations within the expander showing how the pressure reduces the peak value as the monitor points approach the Outlet ports. Our CFD simulations show a pulsating trend of the mass flow rate with the orbiting angle at the Inlet and at the Outlet of the scroll compressor and expander. As documented, the numerical work of Cavazzini et al. [29], Gao et al. [34], Wei et al. [30] also corroborated the presence of a pulsating behavior of the mass flow rate at the Inlet and at the Outlet port of a scroll compressor and expander. These fluctuations are provoked by the periodical blocking effects of the mobile scroll on the Inlet and the Outlet of the machines, and by unsteady inertial phenomena that originate within the chambers of the machines during the discharging phase and cause propagation of the pressure drop back to the Inlet [29, 30]. Besides, superimposing jets of mass travelling inside and outside of the working chambers of the machines also contribute to the periodic fluctuations of the mass flow rates. These phenomena are known as the “porting process” [29, 49]. The “porting process” comprises the merging flows among neighbor chambers, the bridging flow directed toward the discharge chambers, and the discharging flow through the Outlet port. The fluid flow inside a scroll machine is highly three-dimensional, asymmetric, and dynamic. Besides, the high speed of the working fluid and the pulsating phenomena originating inside the two-phase machines may provoke severe vibrations. The numerical studies conducted by Cavazzini et al. [29], Cui [49], Gao et al. [34], Wei et al. [30], Emhardt et al. [32], Emhardt et al. [31], Song et al. [33], and Singh et al. [48] yield similar trends of the velocity distributions within the scroll machines.

With regards to the values of the efficiencies listed in Table 4 and Table 5, we achieve favorable agreements between the results obtained from the CFD simulations and DM computations. Besides, the values of the isentropic and volumetric efficiencies of the two-phase fluid flow twin-scroll compressor obtained numerically from the CFD simulations and from the DM are similar to the ones found experimentally by Bell et al. [14] and by Zhao et al. [18] for a single-phase scroll compressor, and by Fujiwara and Osada [11] and by Seshaiyah et al. [13] for a single-phase fluid flow twin-screw compressor. In addition, the values of the adiabatic efficiency we computed are analogous to the values measured experimentally by Qiu et al. [50] for a scroll expander. Moreover the values of the volumetric efficiency of the expander we obtained numerically are also similar to the values measured experimentally by Mendoza et al. [51] for similar pressure ratios and rotational speeds. The current CFD simulations of two-phase fluid flow twin-scroll compressor and expander have been validated by using the numerical results obtained from the DM and by comparing the outcomes with those available in the literature, although for single-phase fluid flows. In the future, the numerical outcomes obtained from the CDMS can be compared with experimental trials carried out on two-phase twin-scroll compressors and expanders. Besides, the present isothermal formulation of the CDMS will be improved by implementing an energy equation into the solver. The present work represents a starting point for improving the design and optimizing the performance of two-phase flow screw machines. For instance, the leakage space between the fixed and the moving scroll can be optimized to increase the overall efficiency of a two-phase scroll machine by reducing internal leakages. Works in this direction are currently

ongoing.

Position	Max. Skeweness	Max. Non-Orthogonality	Avg. Non-Orthogonality	Max. AR
0°	3.47	82.74	18.06	295.362
90°	3.45	73.26	17.31	172.959
180°	3.11	80.57	17.18	173.555
270°	3.49	88.82	22.59	758.65

Table 6: Mesh quality parameters of the CDMS

Position	Max. Skeweness	Max. Non-Orthogonality	Avg. Non-Orthogonality	Max. AR
0°	2.28	78.23	8.04	836.25
90°	2.39	60.96	7.41	528.44
180°	2.45	50.30	7.61	219.34
270°	2.58	50.99	7.90	200.98

Table 7: Mesh quality parameters by Fadiga et al. [35]

6. Conclusions

In this work, we developed the in-house CDMS, that is, a transient cavitation solver based on the HEM suitable to simulate the inner fluid dynamics of two-phase twin-scroll compressors and expanders. We utilized it to determine important design conditions for the operation of the scroll machines and to pave the way for future optimization of their performances. To build the CDMS, we combine a set of meshed domains of a scroll compressor and expander for different rotation angles with an existing cavitating solver implemented in OpenFOAM[®]. To check the validity of the results obtained with the CDMS, we compared them with the outcomes of a DM available in the literature. Overall, we obtained a very good concordance between the CFD and the DM results. Besides, our CFD results agree qualitatively well with numerical and experimental outcomes available in the literature. Although the CDMS is computationally more expensive than the DM, it allows us to accurately study the inner fluid dynamics of a scroll machine and to investigate the multiphase phenomena that occur while a scroll machine is in operation. Besides, it also permits a close inspection of the “porting process”, that is, processes involve the merging of fluid flow among different chambers that are responsible for the pulsating behavior of the mass flow rate and pressure at the Inlet and Outlet of a scroll machine. In addition, the CDMS delivers important information about the maximum values of the pressure and velocity field allowing us to evaluate whether the investigated scroll machines can be safely operated and/or undergo significant vibrations. Therefore, the current CFD simulations provide in principle experimenters with a valuable predictive tool that can be utilized in the future to optimize two-phase fluid flow twin-scroll machines. Besides, the present version of the CDMS can be upgraded hereafter, for instance, by implementing the energy equation. This will allow us to obtain more precise results and a better understanding of the complex fluid dynamics occurring in two-phase scroll machines.

Nomenclature

PD	Positive Displacement
DM	Deterministic Model
CCHP	Combined Cooling, Heating, and Power
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
CDMS	Cavitating Dynamic Mesh Solver
HEM	Homogeneous Equilibrium Model
RANS	Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes
SST	Shear Stress Transport
CAD	Computer Aided Design

Author Contributions

WL, conception and design of the study, analysis, and interpretation of the data, writing, review, and editing; GL, interpretation of the data, writing, review, and editing; AD, critical revision for important intellectual content; TS, critical revision for important intellectual content. All authors have read and agreed to the submitted version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Interest

Declaration of interest: none

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Figure 8: Pressure distribution on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the compressor for four CAs: $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$

Figure 9: Average pressure distribution in the discharge chamber of the compressor against the orbiting angle. Comparison between the CFD and the DM results

Figure 10: Vapor void fraction on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the compressor for four CAs: $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$

Figure 11: Average vapor void fraction inside the chamber of the compressor against the orbiting angle

Figure 12: Average vapor mass fraction at the Outlet of the compressor against the orbiting angle obtained from the CFD simulations and the DM computations

Figure 13: Comparison between the mass flow rates and their averages at the Inlet a) and at the Outlet b) obtained with the DM and the CFD simulations. The pressure difference between the Inlet and the suction chamber a) and between the Outlet and the discharge chamber b)

Figure 14: Velocity distribution on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the compressor for four CAs: $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$

Figure 15: Pressure distribution on an X-Y section plane of the expander normal to the scroll axis for four CAs: $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$

Figure 16: Average pressure distribution in the discharge chamber of the expander against the orbiting angle. Comparison between the results obtained with the CFD simulations and the DM

Figure 17: Vapor void fraction distribution on an X-Y section plane normal to the scroll axis of the expander for four CAs: $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$

Figure 18: Volume average vapor mass fraction of the expander against the orbiting angle for seven revolutions of the mobile scroll

Figure 19: Average vapor mass fraction at the Outlet port of the expander against the orbiting angle. Comparison between the CFD model and the DM

Figure 20: Comparison between the mass flow rate and the average mass flow rate at the Inlet a) and at the Outlet b) of the expander computed with the DM and the CFD model. Pressure difference between the Inlet and the suction chamber a) and Pressure difference between the Outlet and the discharge chamber b) calculated with the DM and the CFD model

Figure 21: Velocity distribution on an X-Y section plane of the expander normal to the scroll axis for four CAs: $\Phi_c = 90^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 180^\circ$, $\Phi_c = 270^\circ$, and $\Phi_c = 360^\circ$